

P-ISSN: 2349-8528

E-ISSN: 2321-4902

IJCS 2019; 7(4): 2819-2821

© 2019 IJCS

Received: 10-05-2019

Accepted: 12-06-2019

Vanlalmangaihsanga

Department of Livestock
Production and Management,
C.A.U, College of Veterinary
Sciences and A.H., Selesih,
Aizawl, Mizoram, India

L Hmar

Department of Livestock
Production and Management,
C.A.U, College of Veterinary
Sciences and A.H., Selesih,
Aizawl, Mizoram, India

G Kalita

Department of Livestock
Production and Management,
C.A.U, College of Veterinary
Sciences and A.H., Selesih,
Aizawl, Mizoram, India

R Goswami

Department of Livestock
Production and Management,
C.A.U, College of Veterinary
Sciences and A.H., Selesih,
Aizawl, Mizoram, India

AK Samanta

Department of Applied Animal
Nutrition, C.A.U, College of
Veterinary Sciences and A.H.,
Selesih, Aizawl, Mizoram, India

K Lalrintluanga

Department of Veterinary
Animal Reproduction,
Gynaecology and Obstetrics,
C.A.U, College of Veterinary
Sciences and A.H., Selesih,
Aizawl, Mizoram, India

Correspondence**Vanlalmangaihsanga**

Department of Livestock
Production and Management,
C.A.U, College of Veterinary
Sciences and A.H., Selesih,
Aizawl, Mizoram, India

Effect of surgical castration and chemical castrations (AgNO₃ and KMnO₄) on the production performance of growing finishing pigs

Vanlalmangaihsanga, L Hmar, G Kalita, R Goswami, AK Samanta and K Lalrintluanga

Abstract

The study was carried out in 24 LWY male pigs of 2 months reared up to 8 months of age. Three treatment groups of castration namely Control or Surgical Castration (C), Treatment-1 or chemical castration using AGNO₃ (T₁) and Treatment-2 or chemical castration using KMnO₄ (T₂). Each group consist of 8 pigs and castrations were done when the animals reaches the age of 2-3 months for each of the treatment groups. The following parameters were recorded: Fortnightly bodyweight and feed intake. A highly significant ($P < 0.01$) difference was observed in the final body weight and overall ADG; and significant ($P < 0.05$) difference was observed in the overall ADFI and overall FCE of the group T₁ compared to C and T₂ group.

Keywords: LWY, castration, bodyweight, ADG, feed intake, FCE

Introduction

Mizoram is one of the states of North-East India sharing borders with Tripura, Assam and Manipur; and with the neighbouring countries of Bangladesh and Myanmar. Most household in the rural areas of Mizoram reared pigs mainly for domestic consumption and for secondary income. According to the Livestock and Veterinary Economic Survey Mizoram 2017-2018 census and Livestock and veterinary ^[1, 2], the pigs constitute the largest percentage of population for the whole of livestock population in Mizoram. Most of the fattener male pigs in Mizoram are surgically castrated boars. Castration was done when the piglet's reaches the age of 2-3 months of age to remove the boar taint, which were more pronounced upon cooking of the pork when boars were, slaughter un-castrated (Rydhmer, 2010; Bonneau *et al.*, 1992; Cohen *et al.*, 1991; Jaros *et al.*, 2005; Oliver *et al.*, 2003; Patterson, 1968; Pauly *et al.*, 2009) ^[3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. So, surgical castration is followed to remove the boar taint, but the drawback of this surgical castration is that it induced pain due to the incision of the skin and subsequently leading to stress of the animals, which further reduces their growth rate during the first few weeks (Prunier *et al.*, 2015; Hay *et al.*, 2003; Jaturasitha *et al.*, 2006; McGlone and Hellman, 1988; McGlone *et al.*, 1993) ^[10, 11, 12, 13, 14].

Materials and Methods

A total of 24 Large White Yorkshire (LWY) of male pigs of 2 - 3 months age were selected for this experiment. The study was performed at College of Veterinary Sciences & A.H, CAU, Selesih, Aizawl, Mizoram. The pigs were allocated into three different treatment groups (Control, T₁ & T₂) consisting of 8 pigs per group. The first group or control (C) was surgically castrated under local anaesthesia, with all the necessary post-operative treatment. Pigs in the second group or treatment one (T₁), were subjected to chemical castration using 5% silver nitrate solution, which was prepared using 5ml of silver nitrate solution + 95ml distilled water. The solution was injected @ dose of 2ml intra-testicular/testes as per the method of Kang *et al.* (1993) ^[15]. Pigs in the third group or treatment two (T₂) were subjected to chemical castration using 0.25 g potassium permanganate + 17 ml glacial acetic acid + 83 ml sterile distilled water as per the method of Giri *et al.* (2002) ^[16]. These solutions were injected @ dose of 2ml intra-testicular/testes. For T₁ and T₂, the prepared solution was injected using 24 gauge needle syringes. The needle was inserted into the testes from the caudal end of the testes to the caput of the testes.

The solution was injected into the testes while withdrawing the syringe from the testes, so that maximum solution was injected into the whole of the testes.

The individual body weight and total feed intake for each of the pigs was recorded initially at the time of the experiment and subsequently at fortnightly interval till they reach 8 month of age. Then the other production parameters: ADG and FCE were calculated out from the recorded body weights and feed intake.

Results and Discussion

The mean \pm SE fortnightly body weight (kg) of Large White Yorkshire (LWY) male pigs from 2 to 8 months (end of rearing period) of age are presented in the Table 1. Statistical

analysis revealed that the final body weight (kg) of pig in T₁ was significantly higher (100.64 \pm 0.83 kg; $P < 0.01$) as compared to the body weight of pigs under C and T₂ group (94.00 \pm 2.01kg and 91.86 \pm 3.52 kg). The overall ADG (g) in the present study during post-weaning periods in C, T₁ and T₂ were 446.76 \pm 5.24, 483.73 \pm 4.79 and 435.56 \pm 17.95 g respectively, in which T₁ group was significantly higher than C and T₂ group. The present study was comparable to the report of Balaji *et al.* (2006) [17] and Fahim (1994) [18], but higher than the report of AICRP (P) of Assam (2015-16) and Hmar (1993) [19] in LWY. Higher ADG might be due to the fact that in T₁ higher testosterone level was observed which in turn affected the anabolic hormones to enhance growth (Mann and Lutwak-Mann, 1981) [20].

Table 1: Performance of pigs under different method of castration

Fortnight	Treatment group			f Value	p Value
	C	T1	T2		
Fortnightly Body Weight (kg)					
0 th	13.58 \pm 1.94	13.57 \pm 0.70	13.40 \pm 0.76	0.01 ^{NS}	1.00
1 st	18.75 \pm 2.26	24.79 \pm 0.80	18.80 \pm 0.77	1.52 ^{NS}	0.25
2 nd	25.25 \pm 2.31 ^b	30.07 \pm 0.81 ^a	24.80 \pm 0.85 ^{ab}	4.04 ^{**}	0.04
3 rd	33.25 \pm 2.19 ^b	39.21 \pm 0.71 ^a	32.80 \pm 0.82 ^b	6.86 ^{**}	0.01
4 th	41.50 \pm 1.74 ^b	48.14 \pm 0.70 ^a	40.60 \pm 0.83 ^b	12.89 ^{**}	0.001
5 th	49.42 \pm 1.86 ^b	56.71 \pm 0.66 ^a	48.20 \pm 1.07 ^b	13.80 ^{**}	0.001
6 th	57.25 \pm 1.35 ^b	64.36 \pm 0.69 ^a	55.60 \pm 0.81 ^b	23.16 ^{**}	0.001
7 th	64.92 \pm 1.33 ^b	71.64 \pm 0.63 ^a	62.30 \pm 2.10 ^b	13.62 ^{**}	0.001
8 th	72.80 \pm 1.44 ^b	78.86 \pm 0.64 ^a	68.80 \pm 2.20 ^b	15.73 ^{**}	0.001
9 th	78.00 \pm 1.24 ^b	84.71 \pm 0.71 ^a	74.90 \pm 2.57 ^b	11.59 ^{**}	0.001
10 th	83.67 \pm 1.26 ^b	90.29 \pm 0.83 ^a	80.90 \pm 2.49 ^b	10.68 ^{**}	0.001
11 th	89.68 \pm 1.45 ^b	95.57 \pm 0.87 ^a	86.60 \pm 2.71 ^b	8.23 ^{**}	0.004
12 th	94.00 \pm 2.01 ^b	100.64 \pm 0.83 ^a	91.86 \pm 3.52 ^b	4.96 ^{**}	0.02
Average ADG (g/day)	446.76 \pm 5.24 ^b	483.73 \pm 4.79 ^a	435.56 \pm 17.95 ^b	7.21 ^{**}	0.002
Average ADFI (g)	1889.40 \pm 30.97 ^{ab}	1931.00 \pm 12.50 ^a	1821.40 \pm 26.36 ^b	3.97 [*]	0.04
Average FCE	4.23 \pm 0.06 ^b	3.99 \pm 0.04 ^a	4.20 \pm 0.13 ^b	3.97 [*]	0.04

(**) Significant ($P < 0.01$), (*) Significant ($P < 0.05$) and ^{NS} Non-significant

Note: Means bearing at least one common superscript in each row do not differ significantly.

The overall ADFI (g) and FCE in the present study during experimental periods were 1889.40 \pm 30.97g and 4.23 \pm 0.06; 1931.00 \pm 12.50g and 3.99 \pm 0.04; and 1836.40 \pm 26.36g and 4.24 \pm 0.13 respectively in C, T₁ and T₂. Statistical analysis showed a significant ($P < 0.05$) difference among the treatment groups in ADFI and better FCE in T₁ group. The poor FCE in surgically castrated pigs might be due to more energy requirements to produce a unit of body weight, so, when the fats gradually deposited in surgically castrated castrate pigs it required more energy, which led to more feed intake. (Balaji *et al.*, 2006) [17].

Conclusion

From the present study it was observed that pig castrated with Silver Nitrate was found to have best performance in terms of body weight, ADG and FCE. Therefore, from the present research work it may be concluded that chemical castration can be used as an alternate method of castration to surgical castration in reducing the boar taint. But, further research may be carried out on chemical castration for longer rearing period to ascertain the present finding.

References

1. 19th Livestock Census. Government of India, Ministry of Agriculture, Department of Animal Husbandary, Dairy and Fisheries, Krishi Bhawan, New Delhi. 2012, 75.

Dahd.nic.in/sites/default/files/Livestock%20%205.pdf. Accessed on 18th May, 2018.

2. Livestock and veterinary. In: Economic Survey Mizoram, Government of Mizoram, Planning and Programme Implementation Department (Research and Development Branch), 2017-18, 240-248.
3. Rydhmer L, Lundstrom K, Andersson K. Immunocastration reduces aggressive and sexual behaviour in male pigs. *Animal*. 2010; 4(6):965-72.
4. Bonneau M, Meadus WJ, Squires EJ. Effects of exogenous porcine somatotropin on performance, testicular steroid production and fat levels of boar-taint-related compounds in young boars. *Canadian Journal of Animal Science*. 1992; 72(3):537-545.
5. Cohen RDH, King BD, Hunter PSW, Janzen ED. Efficacy of chemical castration and effects of age at castration and implant regime on growth rate, testicular measurements and testosterone levels of beef calves. *Canadian Journal of Animal Science*. 1991; 71(1):1-11.
6. Jaros P, Burgi E, Stark KBC, Claus R, Hennessy D, Thun. Effect of active immunization against GnRH on androstenone concentration, growth performance and carcass quality in intact male pigs. *Livest. Sci*. 2005; 92:31-38.
7. Oliver WT, McCauley I, Harrell RJ, Suster D, Kerton DJ, Dunshea FR. A Gonadotropin-releasing factor vaccine

- (Improvac) and porcine somatotropin have synergistic and additive effects on growth performance in group-housed boars and gilts. *J Anim. Sci.* 2003; 81:1959-1966.
8. Patterson RLS. 5α -androst-16-ene-3-one:—Compound responsible for taint in boar fat. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture.* 1968; 19(1):31-38.
 9. Pauly C, Spring P, O'doherty JV, Kragten SA, Bee G. Growth performance, carcass characteristics and meat quality of group-penned surgically castrated, immunocastrated (Improvac®) and entire male pigs and individually penned entire male pigs. *Animal*, 2009; 3(7):1057-1066.
 10. Prunier A, Bonneau M, Von Borell EH, Cinotti S, Gunn M, Fredriksen B *et al.* A review of the welfare consequences of surgical castration in piglets and the evaluation of non-surgical methods. *Animal Welfare*, 2006; 15:277-289.
 11. Hay M, Vulin A, Genin S, Sales P, Prunier A. Assessment of pain induced by castration in piglets: behavioral and physiological responses over the subsequent 5 days. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 2003; 82:201-218.
 12. Jaturasitha S, Pichitpantapong S, Leangwunta V, Khiaosa-Ard R, Suppadit T, Kreuzer M. Increasing the slaughter weight of boars: Effects on performance and pork quality. *Journal of Applied Animal Research.* 2006; 30(1):19-24.
 13. McGlone JJ, Hellman JM. Local and general anesthetic effects on behaviour and performance of two and seven-week old castrated and uncastrated piglets. *J Anim. Sci.* 1988; 66:3049-3058.
 14. McGlone JJ, Nicholson RI, Hellman JM, Herzog DN. The development of pain in young pigs associated with castration and attempts to prevent castration-induced behavioural changes. *J Anim. Sci.* 1993; 71:1441-1446.
 15. Kang YS, Park CS, Chung HS. Chemical castration by intracellular injection of silver nitrate solution in pigs. *Korean J Anim. Sci.* 1993; 35:463-469.
 16. Giri SC, Yadav BPS, Pand SK. Chemical castration in pigs. *Indian J Anim. Sci.* 2002; 72:451-453.
 17. Balaji NS, Sivaraman T, Sivakumar T, Ramesh V. Influence of castration on growth rate and body measurements in Large White Yorkshire pig. *Indian J Anim Res.* 2006; 40(2):123-126.
 18. Fahim MS. Chemical castration. United States Patent 5372822, Application No. 206469. IOP United States Patent and Trademark Office, 1994. <http://xrint.com/patents/us/5372822>. Accessed on 18th June 2018.
 19. Hmar L. Effect of Weight At Weaning And Plane of Feeding on the Onset of Puberty in Gilts Doctoral dissertation, College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Mannuthy, 1993.
 20. Mann T, Lutwak-Mann C. Male reproductive function and the composition of semen: general considerations. In *Male Reproductive Function and Semen*. Springer, London, 1981, 1-37.